

ASSOCIATION OF NITROTYROSINE AND OXIDIZED LDL IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Background: Type2 Diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is associated with micro and macro vascular complications and it is closely associated increased levels of free fatty acids (FFAs), lipid profile and oxidative stress parameters.

Objectives: The present study aimed to assess the Nitrotyrosine, oxidized LDL levels in T2DM patients compared with healthy volunteers and also to find out the correlative association between nitrotyrosine and oxidized LDL

Materials and methods: Fifty type 2 diabetic patients with age group of 35 to 45 years were selected 50 healthy volunteers age matched subjects were selected as a controls. Plasma nitrotyrosine and oxidized LDL was estimated by ELISA, Glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) was assessed by HPLC method and other routine lipid profile investigations carried out by ERBA EM-360 fully automated analyzer.

Results: Nitrotyrosine and oxidized LDL levels were significantly increased in type 2 diabetic patients. Nitrotyrosine is positively correlated with Oxidised LDL, TGL levels and insulin resistance.

Conclusion: Nitrotyrosine and oxidised LDL are potent oxidative stress markers in type 2 diabetic patients. Regular monitoring of these parameters along with other standard markers might be beneficial to prevent sudden cardiovascular complications.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), Nitrotyrosine (NT), Oxidised LDL (Ox LDL), Insulin resistance evaluation (IR)

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder and concerned as global health burden, Further it was estimated in 2019 as 9 th largest cause of mortality and prevalent in all income levels

(1-3). Early detection of diabetes mellitus through the standard screening procedures to identify asymptomatic individuals will reduce the burden of complications in type 2 diabetes (4).

Nitrotyrosine is a potent oxidant stress biomarker of peroxynitrite (ONOO⁻) and reactive oxidative, nitrosative species (5-7). Protein tyrosine nitration is to be considered as post-translational modification of inflammatory-mediated oxidative stress. Nitrated peptide reflecting an endogenous tyrosine nitration identified in apoA-I recovered from human atherosclerotic plaque (8).

Oxidized LDL term is describe as wide variety of LDL preparations that have been associated with oxidative modifications by ex vivo through defined conditions and other words its isolated from biological sources. Oxidation of LDL reacts with reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) damages LDL and lipid peroxidation (9-10). Ox-LDL molecule upregulation of scavenger receptor A in macrophages, increases monocytes migration at low concentrations and further subsequent foam cell formation (11-13). So the aim of the study was to find out the association between nitrotyrosine and oxidized LDL in type 2 diabetic patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fifty T2DM patients of both sexes with 35-45 of age group on oral hypoglycemic drugs, attending NIMRA institute of medical sciences, Jupudi, Andhra Pradesh, India, were selected for present study. Patients on insulin, thyroid disorders, Smokers, Alcoholics, Tobacco chewers, other active infective diseases, neoplastic disorders, liver dysfunction, history of myocardial infarction, stroke, and occlusive peripheral vascular disease were excluded. Fifty healthy age and sex match subjects were selected as control. The informed consent was obtained from all the study subjects and the study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). Experiments were done in accordance with Helsinki declaration of 1975.

Biochemical analysis:

Fasting blood samples were obtained from the subjects and centrifuged at 2000×g for 10 min. Samples were analyzed for glucose, lipid profile (Total Cholesterol, HDL, LDL, triglycerides) using by ERBA EM-360 fully automated analyzer. Plasma nitrotyrosine, oxidized LDL and Insulin was assessed by Enzyme Linked Immuno Sorbent Assay (ELISA). Routine investigations were carried out by using ERBA auto analyzer. Homeostasis model assessment for insulin resistance evaluation (HOMA-IR) was calculated by fasting plasma insulin × glucose/22.5 (14).

Statistical analysis: Statistical analyses has been carried by SPSS 25.0. Values were expressed as mean ± standard deviation by t-test, p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The Pearson correlation test was used for correlation analysis.

RESULTS**Table 1: Comparison of between baseline parameters Age, BMI, Waist hip ratio, systolic and diastolic blood pressure in between controls and T2DM patients .**

Parameters	Controls (n=50)	T2 DM patients (n=50)	P value
Age	37.9±3.2	40.6±4.3	0.07
Body mass index	25.2±1.5	29.8±1.3	0.04#
Waist/Hip ratio	0.94±0.05	0.98±0.07	0.03#
Systolic BP (mm Hg)	115.4±4.4	140.2±5.5	0.01*
Diastolic (mm Hg)	75.4±3.9	92.1±4.1	0.01*

Data are expressed as mean ±SD, *p<0.001 ,#p<0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Table 2: Comparison between fasting plasma glucose, and postprandial glucose, Lipid profile, HbA1c, Insulin, HOMA-IR, , plasma nitrotyrosine, Ox LDL parameters in controls, T2 DM patients

Parameters	Controls (n=50)	T2 DM patients (n=50)	P value
FPG(mg/dl)	87.3±9.8	153.7±7.9	0.001*
PPG (mg/dl)	105.3±8.6	197.1±12.4	0.001*
Total cholesterol	172.5±8.9	210.5±16.9	0.04#
Serum Triglycerides (mg/dl)	110.6±14.2	196.8±12.8	0.03#
HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	46.1±7.4	38.6±5.8	0.03#
LDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	114.6±11.2	162.8±16.7	0.001*
HbA1c	5.4±0.6	9.8±1.5	0.001*
Insulin (μ IU/ml)	7.3±1.6	14.8±3.2	0.001*
HOMA -IR	1.5±0.15	5.3±2.1	0.001*

Plasma Nitrotyrosine ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	0.31 \pm 0.06	0.64 \pm 0.12	0.001*
Ox LDL(U/L)	82.4 \pm 10.2	136.9 \pm 8.7	0.001*

Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, * $p < 0.001$, # $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Table 4: Correlation between Plasma Nitrotyrosine & measured parameters in study subjects

Parameters	Correlation Coefficient- r	P value
Ox LDL	0.398	0.04*
FPG	0.321	0.07
PPG	0.398	0.02*
HbA1c	0.375	0.01**
HOMA-IR	0.421	0.01**
Cholesterol	0.198	0.06
TGL	0.411	0.04*
HDL	-0.271	0.07
LDL	0.321	0.04*

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

DISCUSSION

Reactive nitrogen species with biomolecules is the nitration of protein tyrosine residues in the ortho position to the phenolic hydroxyl group will form as 3-nitrotyrosine. Tyrosine nitration affects different physicochemical properties of the amino acid residues and corresponding proteins such as decrease in the pKa of the phenolic hydroxyl group, from 10.2 to \sim 7.2 for the free amino acids in aqueous solution; this decrease will be affected by the protein environment(15-17). Tyrosine-nitrated proteins are detected in cells and tissues under normal physiological conditions, revealing a basal continuous flux of nitrating species; the levels of nitrated proteins are strongly increased under conditions of enhanced formation of $\bullet\text{NO}$ and/or oxidants, and they are typically strongly associated with disease onset and progression (18-19). In the present study we observed there was significant increased nitrotyrosine levels in type 2 diabetic patients compared with healthy controls and also there was positive association with oxidized levels by through pearson correlation anlysis. That means the increased and OX LDL triggers the endothelial dysfunction and promotes the vascular dysfunction and complications in diabetic patients.

Oxidized low-density lipoprotein (ox-LDL) is a prooxidant derived from native LDL by cell-mediated oxidation (20). Lipid profile changes / alterations of lipoproteins are considered to

be potent oxidative stress in diabetes, oxidative stress and oxidatively modified LDL by aldehyde products creating a net negative charge which were essential for its interaction and uptake by macrophages and also this will contribute towards oxidation by different lipid oxidants further it will promote atherosclerosis (21-22).

The present study showed significant increased HBA1C, Insulin resistance, total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL cholesterol and decreased HDL cholesterol levels in diabetic patients compared with healthy controls as reported earlier studies. Hyperglycemia along with glucose fluctuations, dyslipidemias have demonstrated the ability to increase atherothrombotic risk in type 2 diabetic patients by through promoting platelet aggregation through arachidonic acid signalling pathway (23-26). So increased OX LDL is one of the contribute factor for tyrosine nitration in proteins and leads to endothelial dysfunction and vascular complications in diabetic patients.

CONCLUSION

Nitrotyrosine and oxidised LDL are potent oxidative stress markers in type 2 diabetic patients. Regular monitoring of these parameters along with other standard markers might be beneficial to prevent sudden cardiovascular complications.

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